

Virtual Learning Environment: Enriching 21st Century Academic Landscape

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Abstract:

Virtual learning environments (VLEs) play a crucial role in the academe. Put on spotlight during the Covid-19 Pandemic, VLEs enable educators to reach out to their learners as they can easily communicate and interact with their students to facilitate learning beyond their classrooms and typically limited class time. Moreover, VLEs empower learners as they can easily communicate, collaborate, access learning materials, upload assignments and requirements, answer online quizzes, and seek their teachers' assistance in spite of the lack of personal interaction in online and blended learning

modalities. Recent studies suggest that VLEs foster collaboration, communication, and interaction among the primary stakeholders – teachers and students – of the academe. This journal article aims to shed light on the nature and significance of virtual learning environments as it enriches the academic landscape of the 21st century. Delving into the significant findings of recent studies, this article will elucidate the numerous issues and challenges encountered by the primary stakeholders of the academe. Finally, it shall point out the gaps in the current research literature to underscore the fascinating and timely topics which may be considered by future researchers in their pursuit of knowledge creation.

Keywords: *virtual learning environment, VLE, issues, challenges, academic landscape.*

Introduction

Virtual learning environments (VLEs) have been useful especially during the Covid-19 Pandemic. Though its use has flaws and several areas for improvement, VLEs were found to be effective in enabling teachers to reach out to their students. As teachers create and diligently maintain their VLEs, they can easily communicate and interact with their students to facilitate learning beyond their classrooms. Moreover, VLEs empower students as they can easily communicate, collaborate, access learning materials, upload assignments and requirements,

answer online quizzes, and seek their teachers' assistance in spite of the lack of personal interaction in online and blended learning modalities. Recent studies (Al Ruheili & Al-Saidi, 2015; Al Said, 2015; Bayburtsyan, 2016; Dayag, 2018; Mustafa, 2015; Torres Martin, C., Acal, C., El Honrani, M., & Mingorance Estrada, Á.C., 2021) suggest that VLEs facilitate learning, and foster collaboration, communication, and interaction among the primary stakeholders – teachers and students – of the academe.

Background

A number of empirical studies ascertained that teachers and learners have a positive attitude towards VLEs, and that VLEs have a positive impact on the learners' academic progress (Al-Kathiri, 2014; Al-Ruheili and Al-Saidi, 2015; Al-Said, 2015; Bicen, 2014; Dayag, 2018). VLEs also promote interaction and collaboration among the learners (Kear, 2007; Dayag, 2018) as these provide functional communication tools that allow both the learners and educators to communicate and collaborate in different settings and modalities (Al-Kathiri, 2014; Warner, 2013). Moreover, VLEs were perceived to have a positive effect on the learners' interaction with their classmates and teachers, as well as their dynamic participation in the different activities in the classroom (Al-Kathiri, 2014, Al-Ruheili & Al-Saidi, 2015; Al-Said, 2015; Balasubramanian, Jaykumar & Fukey, 2014; Dayag, 2018; Mimirinis & Bhattacharya, 2007; Torres Martin, C., Acal, C., El Honrani, M., & Mingorance Estrada, Á.C.,2021).

In various contexts, several empirical studies found out that VLEs are perceived by learners as a useful and functional tool that provides a secured and encouraging learning environment that empowers them to deepen their knowledge, process deeply and subconsciously their lessons, and improve their communication and higher order thinking skills (Al-Kathiri, 2014; Al-Ruheili & Al-Saidi, 2015; Al-Said, 2015; Bicen, 2014; Dayag, 2018). Furthermore, VLEs are considered by learners as helpful learning environments as these enrich their learning experiences and give them varied opportunities to explore and assimilate their lessons (Bataneh & Mayyas, 2017; Dayag, 2018; Morris & Rippin, 2003).

In spite of the significant number of empirical studies conducted thus far, it is obvious that further research on virtual learning environments need to be conducted in order to shed more light on the impact, functional features, perceptions, and challenges that the different stakeholders encounter while using VLEs.

What are Virtual Learning Environments (VLEs)?

The term virtual learning environments has been given several definitions. Hence, the word may simply be understood by the primary stakeholders as “a learning environment on the cloud” that provides them a valuable avenue for sharing information and instructional materials, communication, collaboration and interaction. VLEs refer to a specific form of e-learning technology that uses networked computers to provide a range of functions to educators and learners (O’Leary, 2004). VLEs may also pertain to a virtual classroom created in a web-based learning platform, software or learning management system created by an educator for his learners, primarily for academic purposes (Martins & Kellermanns, 2004; O’Leary & Ramsden, 2002). Nowadays, VLEs are typically created in various platforms like Moodle, Edmodo, Blackboard, Canvas, D2L Brightspace, Schoology and Google Classroom.

From a wider perspective, VLEs are characterized by the following: a) a designed information and social space, b) learners are engaged and active participants (co-creators) of this virtual space, and c) varied technologies and pedagogical approaches are integrated (Dillenbourg, Schneider & Synteta, 2002). In other words, VLEs are online avenues for communication, collaboration, and sharing of valuable materials/ resources for academic purposes.

VLE’s Significance

Through the years, VLEs have become a significant part of the 21st century academic landscape. It is noteworthy that VLEs have played a pivotal role during the COVID-19 pandemic. VLEs have become more functional as the academe leverages the use of technology (tablets, laptop computers, smartphones,etc.) and blended learning beyond the confines of the traditional classrooms and the limitations of class hours (Dayag, 2018; Kukulska-Hulme et al., 2011; Scully, 2008; Tuzlukova, Al-Busaidi, Coombe & Stojkovic, 2016).

VLEs empower teachers as it provides them an avenue to share with their students their learning materials, quizzes, rubrics and announcements. As well, VLEs enable educators to promote interaction, active learning, collaboration and communication with their students. Recent studies suggest that VLEs enrich the 21st century academic landscape.

Meanwhile, VLEs empower learners as they can easily communicate, collaborate, access learning materials, upload homework and requirements, answer online quizzes, and seek assistance from their teachers and classmates.

Considering the other stakeholders in the academe, VLEs are equally useful to the educational leaders and parents as these are helpful and efficient in disseminating information and updates regarding the learners' academic progress, requirements, etc.

Features of VLEs

VLEs are helpful in the academe due to their ever-improving, functional features that are continually refined and/or re-designed to maximize the benefits the stakeholders gain from using these VLEs in their particular context (Al Ruheili & Al-Saidi, 2015; Al Said, 2015; Bayburtsyan, 2016; Dayag, 2018; O'Leary & Ramsden, 2002).

- **Communication.** Educators and learners can easily communicate with one another in VLEs. They may use the chat box and discussion board that support various types of communication: synchronous and asynchronous, one-to-one, one-to-many and many-to-many.
- **Assessment.** Educators can provide their learners materials for self-assessment and/or summative assessment. For example, they may create multiple-choice assessments with automated marking and immediate feedback. Moreover, educators may upload all the rubrics or criteria which can serve as the learners' guide in drafting and improving their requirements like essays, research reports, and reaction papers.

- **Uploading of learning resources and materials.** Educators—and even their learners—make the teaching and learning materials available to their learners. They may upload instructional materials, images, audio and video clips, links to other online resources, and assessment activities. With some advanced VLEs, educators can schedule the automatic uploading of assignments, quizzes and projects, hence they may easily follow their syllabus or pacing guide.

- **Collaboration.** Educators may encourage their learners to upload and share files in their VLEs. They may also give pairwork or group work which fosters collaboration and cooperation among the learners. The learners may likewise be allowed to work together both in synchronous or asynchronous settings.

- **Privacy.** Educators can ensure that only the official students enrolled can access and use the materials in their VLEs. The learners may feel a strong sense of belongingness as their VLEs provide a safe and secure environment where they can raise questions and points for clarification, share their insights, and elicit feedback from their teacher or classmates.

Characteristics of VLEs

The best and most functional VLEs have the following characteristics:

- **Teacher-friendly** (assessment, feedback, content-management). VLEs are basically teacher-friendly as these help the teacher in terms of assessing students' academic progress, providing feedback to their students and managing the quizzes, assignments, etc.
- **Student-friendly.** The best VLEs are student-friendly. These can help the students advance or learn at the comfort of their homes and during their free or convenient time.
- **Interactive** (teacher-students; student-students). VLES foster a vibrant interaction between students and their teachers. It also promotes interaction among students especially when they work in groups or pairs.

- **Personalized.** With the wonderful features of VLEs, teachers can make the VLEs personalized so that students feel they belong.
- **Secured.** The best VLEs are generally secured, hence both the teachers and students feel comfortable in submitting their academic outputs.
- **Sustainable.** VLEs (especially the free ones) are typically sustainable, hence teachers and students can use these freely wherever they are or whenever they like to.
- **Cost-effective.** From the perspective of students, VLEs are cost-effective as these allow them to save the money, which they usually spend for transportation, printing, etc.

Challenges and Concerns Related to VLEs

The stakeholders of the academe encounter numerous issues or challenges pertinent to VLEs. Some of these issues include technical issues, lack of face-to-face interaction, potential for isolation, limited flexibility, lack of personalization, and cost.

- **Technical issues.** Users may encounter technical glitches while using VLEs. Both the educators and learners may experience server crashes, slow internet speeds, or software glitches, although these happen less frequently nowadays. One remedy for slow internet speed which results in accessibility issues is uploading MS Word files if possible (O’Leary & Ramsden, 2002). It is definitely easier to access texts (small file size) than video or audio files which may take much time to download, and lead to the learners leaving the VLE.
- **Lack of face-to-face interaction.** VLEs are typically used in online or distance learning environments, which means that students may not enjoy the benefits of face-to-face interaction with teachers and their classmates. In the long run, students may find it difficult to get along well with their classmates and teachers. In addition, they may find it hard to engage in collaborative learning activities.

- **Potential for isolation.** Students who are using a VLE may feel isolated if they do not interact regularly with their teachers and classmates.

- **Limited flexibility.** A number of VLEs are designed to support specific types of learning activities or pedagogical styles that may limit their flexibility. With different teaching and learning contexts, teachers and students may find it more challenging to create appropriate learning experiences that are purported to address the needs and preferences of the students.

- **Lack of personalization.** VLEs may not provide personalized learning experiences if these are not carefully designed and judiciously planned. VLEs must be carefully planned and designed to address the learners’ needs and learning objectives.

- **Cost.** Albeit some VLEs are free, others are expensive and costly to maintain as they require subscription fees or financial support for maintenance. Hence, it is important for educators to create VLEs in platforms or learning management systems, which are appropriate to their academic context.

Besides the challenges occasionally encountered by VLE-users, a number of concerns must be addressed to make VLEs both successful and sustainable. These concerns include the learners’ interest to learn beyond their comfort zone, the educators’ interest to reach out to their learners through the varied features of the VLEs they use, the educational leaders’ interest to support the educators in using VLEs (especially those that require subscription), and time allotment and/ or management (Dayag, 2018). Cognizant of the educators’ diverse duties and responsibilities that usually make their schedule hectic, educators have to go the extra mile in creating and sustaining VLEs if they want to make their learners truly engaged and eventually realize the significance of VLEs in their academic journey. They need to be consistent in uploading announcements or the necessary instructional materials (like worksheets and Google Form links) in order to motivate the

learners to use their respective VLEs regularly (Al-Kathiri, 2014, Al-Ruheili & Al-Saidi, 2015; Al-Said, 2015; Balasubramanian, Jaykumar & Fukey, 2014; Dayag, 2018; Mimirinis & Bhattacharya, 2007). Once the learners realize the significance of their VLEs, they will eventually appreciate the use of VLEs regardless of their academic setting.

Future Research Directions: Ways Forward

With the increasing popularity of VLEs especially at the outset of the COVID-19 pandemic, the authors would like to point out the gaps and significance of conducting relevant studies—either meta-analyses or empirical studies—that may shed light on the various features, perspectives and challenges related to the use of virtual learning environments in varied academic contexts.

1. Conduct a meta-analysis on the impact of VLEs in different academic settings (elementary, secondary, tertiary, graduate school).
2. Conduct a meta-analysis on the effectiveness of VLEs in different geographic locations (E.g. North America, South America, Asia, Europe, Australia, etc.).
3. Conduct an empirical study that would delve into the effectiveness of the different features of VLEs.
4. Conduct an empirical study that would compare two well-used VLEs in terms of the different features.
5. Conduct an empirical study that would delve into the perception of students on their VLEs (post-pandemic context).
6. Conduct an empirical study that would delve into the perception of teachers on their VLEs (post-pandemic context).
7. Conduct an empirical study that would delve into the perception of educational leaders and parents on the use of VLEs (post-pandemic context).
8. Conduct a longitudinal study that would delve into the impact of VLEs to learners who started using VLEs from elementary to their secondary education.
9. Conduct a longitudinal study that would delve into the impact of VLEs to learners who started using VLEs from elementary until their tertiary education.
10. Conduct a longitudinal study that would delve into the issues and challenges encountered by the teachers and students while using their VLEs.
11. Conduct comprehensive empirical studies that would delve into the impact of VLEs in learning, teaching and assessment.
12. Conduct comprehensive empirical studies that would delve into the effect of VLEs on developing learner autonomy, active learning, collaboration and communication through the conduct of experimental, or quasi-experimental studies in different contexts.
13. Conduct an empirical study that would compare the efficiency of a paid VLE and a free VLE in terms of features, functionality, support, etc.

Conclusion

Virtual learning environments have enriched—and will continually do so—the current academic landscape, which keeps evolving and becoming more flexible, more fascinating and more dynamic beyond the confines of traditional classrooms and the restrictions of class hours. Like any other technological advancements used in education, VLEs are far from perfect. Nonetheless, many VLEs have functional features that help educators facilitate learning and teaching; hence, these can supplement and support on-site teaching and learning. In a nutshell, VLEs are deemed useful despite the several challenges encountered by the primary stakeholders (educators and learners) of the academe. For the educators and educational leaders engaged in knowledge creation, they may consider VLEs as one of the relevant and timely themes that need further research.

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